

POVERTY AND PROSTITUTION SUSCEPTIBILITY AMONGST FEMALE YOUTHS IN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

Ottong, Inimfon Joseph
Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus
inimfonottong@aksu.edu.ng. 08065298008

Abstract

There are myriad factors that seem to encourage or favour prostitution, especially among young people. This study aimed to examine the influence of poverty on the susceptibility of prostitution among female youths in Cross River State, Nigeria. The survey adopted an inferential design. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 300 respondents (250 females and 50 males). The questionnaire was the primary instrument for data collection. Data were analysed using both descriptive statistics with excerpt from interview for triangulation of findings. Null hypothesis was tested with and the results showed that there is existing positive relationship between poverty and prostitution in Cross River State. The hypothesis test demonstrated through Pearson's Product-moment Correlation coefficient $r = 0.97$ show a statistically significant relationship between poverty and susceptibility of prostitution among young girls. This study confirms that poverty encourages prostitution among female youths in Cross River State, Nigeria. It is therefore recommended that the government make a concerted effort to create employment opportunities and develop platforms that will help generate wealth for the large unemployed population in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Poverty, Prostitution, Susceptibility, Female youths, and Sex workers.

Introduction

Prostitution, otherwise known as commercial sex work has existed in all societies and holds a place as the world's oldest profession. Over the years prostitution has grown into every sector of life. The types have also become diversified and the trend and dimension has gotten to a level that the society is disturbed. Not only might the growth of prostitution be a threat to society but it may also contribute to deviant behaviour (Lankford & Howard, 2024). In colloquial usage, the word "prostitution" is sometimes generalised to mean the selling of one's service for cause thought to be unworthy. Prostitution describes sexual intercourse in exchange for remuneration. The Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary defines prostitution as the work of a prostitute - the work that is done to earn money but people do not respect it and the worker. In other words, having sex for money and someone who engages in sexual promiscuity comes under prostitution (Ward & Welling, 2015).

Prostitutes are not the only people who have sex for money. Porn actors and actresses get paid for having sex, but they are both paid by the third party the producer. The person with whom she/he has sex pays prostitute. Male prostitutes offering their services to male customers are called "hustlers" or "rent boys" while male prostitute offering services to female customers are known as "gigolo" (Ward & Welling, 2015). Prostitutes are stigmatized

in most societies and religions; their customers are typically stigmatised to a lesser degree. The sexual counterparts of prostitutes are known as Johns in the united place, men who drive around for the purpose of soliciting prostitutes are also known as kerb crawlers (Dickson, 2016).

In escort prostitution, the act takes place at the customer place at the residence or more commonly at his or her hotel room, (currently referred to as “out-calls”) or at the escort's place of residence or in a hotel rented for the occasion by the escort's called “in-called”. This form of prostitution often shelters under the umbrella of escort agencies that ostensibly supply attractive escorts for social occasions. While escort agencies claim never to provide sexual services, very few successful escorts are available exclusively for social companionship. Even where prostitution is legal, the euphemistic term “escort service” is common (Ward & Welling, 2015).

Cameron (2018) observed that in the United States of America, escort agencies advertise frequently on the World Wide Web, and example advertisement can be readily found on any major search engine and on open forum sites such as Craig list. In some cases, prostitutes use the internet to place advertisements, or prospective customers could so advertise for a prostitute. Some escorts may work independently of an agency. This is achieved by advertising the services on offer directly in newspapers, magazines or internet. Communication clients are usually made on a telephone and appointments are negotiated without any third-party involvement (Kinnell, 2014).

Escort agencies typically advertise in regional publications and even telephone listings like the yellow pages. Many maintain websites with photo galleries of the employers. An interested client contacts an agency by telephone and offers a description of what kind of escort they are looking for; the agency will then suggest an employee who might fit the client's contact information and calls the escort. Usually, to protect the identity of the escort and ensure effective communication with the client, the agency arranges the appointment. Church *et al.* (2011) opines that sometimes it may be up to the escorts to contact the clients directly to make arrangements for location and time of an appointment. If the agency does not supply transport to and from the client, the escort is also expected to call the agency upon arrival at location and again upon leaving to assure his or her self-completion of the booking. The purpose of these details is to protect the escort agency (to some degree) from prosecution for breaking the law. If the employee is solely responsible for arranging illegal aspects of their professional encounter, the agency could try to maintain plausible deniability should an arrest be made.

Most transactions occur in cash, and optional tipping of escorts by client in most major Nigerian cities like Port Harcourt, Lagos and Abuja; this is customary but not compulsory (Achu, 2015). Independent escorts, also known as providers, have differing fees depending on many factors, for example, different seasons brings about cost, as do regular and semi-regular customers. Some charge by the hour, half or even in 15 minutes blocks. Time extensions if offered or requested are usually priced at the same rate as the original booking. Some escorts pay another to act as their personal security, thus providing a level of protection to themselves from violent or abusive clients. An escort who works less often may be able to command a premium for his or her services exclusively. One who sees several clients each day may charge less, but earn more in the end. Independent escorts might see

clients for extended meetings involving dinner or social activities, whereas escorts who work through agencies generally provide sexual services. Whilst the vast majority of escort agencies are sex related, there are some non-sexual escort agencies, where escorts provide companionship for business and social occasions.

The background here tries to highlight factors that seem to encourage or favour prostitution in the study area. Beginning in the late 1980s, many States increased the penalties for prostitution in cases where the prostitute is known to be HIV positive (Chudakov & IILan, 2022). These laws, often known as felony prostitution laws in the U.S.A., certainly not in Nigeria, require anyone arrested for prostitution to be tested for HIV, and if the test comes back positive, the suspect is then informed that any future arrest for prostitution will be a felony instead of a misdemeanour. Penalties for felony prostitution vary in the States that have such laws, with maximum sentences of typically 10 to 15 years in prison. So far in Nigeria and Cross River State, there are no laws in this respect. As a result, the rate of prostitution, otherwise called commercial sex work, has increased alarmingly, and there is no hope for the reduction and even eradication, especially in this era where unemployment, poverty and the like hold sway.

According to Peters and Bassey (2019), poverty in Sub-Saharan Africa has been a great issue of discourse among cooperate bodies and governments all over the world, with the major and first Sustainable Development Goal being “No Poverty”. Prostitution is primarily the outcome of multiple adverse social, economic, cultural and family conditions. To prevent prostitution, it is imperative to have an understanding of its roots. These are complex and interrelated but can be summarised in three categories: Economic Factors/Poverty: in addition to lack of financial resources, poverty manifests itself in a lack of educational opportunities, lack of meaningful employment options, poor housing, lack of hope and the prejudice against a person living in poverty. The factors mentioned above have led a lot of girls and males to involve themselves in prostitution. Understandably, an underpowered person is a veritable instrument in the "wheel" of destruction. The majority of the people who are prostitutes are not there by choice, but by circumstances.

Prostitution has often been associated with the spread of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) such as HIV, syphilis, gonorrhoea, etc. Although prostitutes are not regularly studied, as other institutions/ what little has been done on the subject suggests that female prostitutes have higher chances of contracting HIV/AIDs and other related sexually transmitted diseases. Intravenous drug-using prostitutes carry a very high rate of HIV/AIDs relative to the population. Many others, especially child prostitutes, are prone to V.V.F., dislodgement and bruising of the vulva and cervix, which have consequences. The majority take pills to prevent pregnancy, outside a doctor's prescription, which might result in the blockage of the womb and may eventually lead to cancer and death (Hughes & Roch, 2019). The majority are made to take hard drugs. Smoke marijuana, sniff cocaine and a wide range of caffeinated drinks, which health implications is grievous. It was against this background and problem that this study was initiated to examine the influence of poverty on prostitution among female youths in Cross River State.

Literature Review

Causes of Prostitution

An individual needs to be responsible for his or her own actions. An understanding of root causes cannot and should not be seen as a way to absolve us from personal accountability. However/ while individuals have obligation to act responsibly and with respect for their fellow citizens/ communities have a responsibility to address those conditions, which hinder healthy development and can become the breeding ground for prostitution.

The root causes of prostitution are well documented and researched. Prostitution is primarily the outcome of multiple adverse social, economic, cultural and family conditions. To prevent prostitution it is imperative to have an understanding of its roots. These are complex and interrelated but can be summarized in three categories, Economic Factors/Poverty: in addition to lack of financial resources, poverty manifests itself in a lack of educational opportunities, lack of meaningful employment options, poor housing, lack of hope and the prejudice against person living in poverty.

These mentioned above, has made a lot of girls and males to involve themselves in prostitution. Understandably an underpowered person is a veritable instrument in the "wheel" of destruction. Majority of the persons that are prostitutes are not there by choice, but by circumstances. A cursory look at prostitution and prostitutes in Cross River State shows that, poverty, unemployment, no access to education and the likes account largely as the causes of prostitution.

Social and environmental factors equally predisposed people to prostitution. Our social structure mirrors to citizens and communities what we value and how we set priorities. Social root causes of prostitution are inequality, not sharing power, lack of support to families and neighbourhoods, real or perceived inaccessibility to services, lack of leadership in communities, low value placed on children and individual well-being and the over exposure to television as a means of recreation.

The family structure is another very important factor that makes or unmakes an individual to go into prostitution. It is belief that, the families are uniquely placed in contributing to members of society. But the task of putting children first goes beyond the family to raising healthy responsible communities and society. Dysfunctional family conditions contribute to prostitution and other untoward behaviour and these conditions include; parental inadequacy, parent conflict, parental criminality/prostitution, lack of respect and responsibility, abuse and neglect of children and family violence which lead to unwanted teenage pregnancy (Ottong et al., 2025),

Types of Prostitution.

Prostitutes use several strategies to maintain a positive self-image in the face of social condemnation and rejection. The types of prostitutes include the following:

(a) Housewife Prostitution

Though this type of prostitution is not overly popular it still remains the oldest form of prostitution. It is a form of prostitution where a legally married woman subtly indulges in prostitution to earn extra money or some other material benefit. Unconfirmed source, report that there is a community in Cross River State that husbands encourage their wives to go for prostitution. According to this unconfirmed report, this is done to prove the woman's beauty and strength of womanhood.

(b) Street Prostitution

In street prostitution, the prostitute solicits customers while waiting at street corners, usually "dressed workers" while their customers are referred to as "tricks". (Boynton, 2006) The sex is performed in the customer's care, in a nearby alley, or in a rented room (motels that service prostitutes the rented rooms could be by the half or full hour). There are beautiful, vibrant and daring girls, they sleep at daytime and operate at night - seductively dressed to attract would be customers. Their targets are the rich play boys and middle-aged businessmen, seeking fun outside marital home for those who are married. Negotiation and transactions take place in the car, the customer's chosen abode and even hotel room. They actually makes a lot of money but the risk implication is so enormous. They could be attacked by thieves, hoodlums and ritual killers-who pose as customers.

c) Campus prostitution

As the name implies, this type of prostitution is domiciled in the campuses, usually carried out by Universities, Colleges of Education and Polytechnic students. These categories of prostitutes are driven by greed and desperation for money and other material and ostentatious living. They grace the bed of politicians especially the law-makers (senators/ representative members, the ministers and commissioners - retired generals, governors, captains of industries and the likes. Campus prostitution seems to be the best, because they seem to make a lot of money with less stress. More laughable is the fact that, the operators do not see it as prostitution rather; it is termed "big-chick" and "the happening babe". Majority of them retire after graduation from the University.

(d) Brothel Prostitution

This is a resident kind of prostitution where customers visits and get their fun and pay. Usually charges are done depending on the time. Some customers can stay for duration of one hour, others may stay for thirty minutes, and still some could stay for five minutes and pay accordingly. Certainly the longer you stay the higher you pay. In this category, there are full and part time brothel prostitutes. What the part timers do is stay outside and at night and visit the brothel and clubs where the render/offer their service to men. While the full time brothel prostitutes, domiciled there and do their business of sex there.

(e) Corporate Prostitutes

These categories involve relatively advanced ladies from the ages of 25 to 48, most times called professional contractors or businesswomen. People hardly know that, they are prostitutes. These ladies sleep with government officials and captain of industries, to get contracts, others sleep with magistrate to win cases for their clients, Female politicians sleeping with male politicians to support them in election and other sundry services. Laso is the sexual prostitution at work places (Akpan et al., 2024).

(f) Child Prostitution

This type of prostitution is very disturbing and presently is on the increase. These are minor as young as 12, 13 and 14 years old, found in brothels, streets and other strategic place soliciting for sex for money. These girls work for their so-called 'Madam' and after sleeping with men, give money to them. If prostitution in general is legal, there is usually a minimum age requirement for legal prostitution that is higher than the general age of consent. Although some countries do not single out patronage of child prostitution as a separate crime, some act is punishable as sex with an underage.

Socio-Economic and Legal Status of Prostitution

Prostitution has some social implications on the individual and the society. Prostitute and prostitution is stigmatized and looked denigrated. The society generally frowns at this rather untoward profession embarked upon by people for whatever reasons. Certainly a society that is associated with prostitution is seen as incompatible with human dignity and therefore violates the fundamental human rights, regardless of the gender/ race, ethnicity or class. The society is seen as been opaque to the moral ethos that guides the moral rectitude of a society and humanity. Obviously, such individual and society are treated disdainfully amongst comity of nations and friends. It is expected that/ any girl from that setting outside her locality is seen as a potential prostitute. For example, if any Nigerian woman is seen in the Streets of Italy it is expected that she is a prostitute.

Socially prostitution derogates a person and reduces one's personality put differently/ especially in cross River State/ women perceived as prostitutes hardly get married because the society sees them as evil and worthless. At one of the legal spectrum/ prostitution carries the death penalty in some Muslim countries, at the end; prostitutes are tax paying and unionized professionals in the Netherlands and brothels are legal and advertising business there. The legal situation in Germany, Switzerland and New Zealand is similar to the Netherlands, In the Australian State of New Wales, any person over the age of 18 years may offer to provide sexual services in return for money (Boies,1994).

In Victoria, a person who wishes to run a prostitution business must have a license. Prostitutes working for themselves in their business, as prostitutes in the business, must be registered. Individual sex workers are not required to be registered or licensed. In some countries the legal status of prostitution may vary depending on the activity; in Japan, for example, the vaginal prostitution is against the law while fellatio prostitution is legal, as women who perform fellatio for money are not considered prostitute in Japan.

In Turkey, street prostitution is illegal prostitution, although government regulated brothel is legal. All brothels must have a license and all sex workers working in brothels must be licensed as well. Municipality based commissions for the struggle against Venereal diseases and prostitution are in charge of issuing such licenses. In the United Kingdom, prostitution is not formally illegal, but several activities surrounding it is outlawed. (Modan, 1982).

Rules vary as to which roles in prostitution are illegal: being a prostitute, being a client, or being a pimp. In Sweden it is legal to sell sex, but it is illegal to be a pimp and since 1999 also to buy sexual services. The reason for this law is to protect prostitutes, as many of them have been forced into prostitution by someone or economy necessity. Prostitutes are generally viewed by government as oppressed, while their client or pimp is illegal, but being the prostitute is not, except if the client is a sounder aged (under 18). Most countries criminalize prostitution; prostitutes are arrested and prosecuted at a far higher rate than their clients.

Prostitution is legal for citizens in Denmark, but it is illegal to profit from prostitution. Prostitution is not regulated in the Netherlands; instead, the government attempts through social services to bring people out of prostitution into other careers, and attempts to lessen the amount of criminal activity and other negative effects of prostitution. (Chudakor, 2003)

Engagements in sexual slavery or owned by organized crime are the highest priority targets of law enforcement actions against prostitution. Policies also frequently intervene when promoted by local residents complaints/ often directed against street prostitution. In most countries where prostituted on is illegal, at least some forms of it are tolerated. This ambiguous status allows the police to extort money or services, particularly information on criminal activities that prostitutes are often well placed to obtain from prostitution in exchange for "working the other way".(Mallory,2005)

Pimping is a sex crime in almost all jurisdictions some other countries retain the ill - defined offences of living off the proceeds of other's prostitution; one of the prima face evidences of which is co-habiting with prostitute. In 1949, the UN General Assembly adopted a convention stating that, forced prostitution is incompatible with human dignity, requiring all signing parties to punish pimps and brothel owners and operators and abolish special treatment or registration of prostitutes.

Theoretical Framework

Marxian Theory

The proponent of this theory is Karl Marx- in his *Das Kapital* (1867-1894) which provides the intellectual foundation for explaining why prostitution in the society. Marxian theory opines that wealth is concentrated in the hands of the minority, those who own the forces of production (bourgeoisie) who subject the masses (proletariat) to servitude conditions. They decide the conditions of service for the masses without their consent. Hence the standard of pay and condition of work influence their decision to make 'ends meet. From the Marxian perspective prostitution can be understood in terms of the system of inequality generated by the capitalist economy. Since the market forces, which seem to control production are impersonal mechanisms beyond the control of man, the subjected class then takes on the character of bestial labour, which is prostitution.

However, in order to survive, members of the subject class are forced to sell their bodies in return for wages. The object of such act as translated in prostitution involves, long standing hours, dangerous and often unhealthy places of transaction, exploitation, oppression; sometimes - outright intimidations and abuse. Thus, it is contended that, prostitution is for the subject class work that becomes the most viable and attainable means in which they could improve their conditions.

Methodology

Study area

The survey inferential design was adopted for the study. This study was conducted in Cross River State, Nigeria, which shares a common boundary with the Republic of Cameroon in the East, Benue State in the North, Ebonyi and Abia States in the West, and Akwa Ibom State in the South West. It has a population of 2,888,966 according to the 2006 census. It lies within longitudes $4^{\circ} 30'$ and $7^{\circ} 10'$ North. There are eighteen local government areas in the State, each of which is headed by an elected chairman. The culture of Cross River State has expressed in the languages, dressing, festivals, traditional dances, etc. There are exciting tourist centres such as Qua falls, Agbokim waterfalls, Obudu Ranch Resort just to mention a few. Occupationally, the majority of Cross River State engage in farming while a few others

find themselves in petty trading and transport business. The state enjoys two different major climatic conditions, namely, the dry and the rainy seasons (November to April and May to October) respectively.

Cross River State was one of the centres of education in Nigeria. Many late and living nationalists attended the famous Hope Waddel Training Institution, Calabar. Today, there is the University of Calabar and the State University of Technology, which operate three campuses in Calabar, Ogoja, and Akamkpa. It also has a College of Health Technology in Calabar, as well as other institutions of higher learning. Besides these, there also abound numerous public and private secondary, primary and nursery schools. Politically, Calabar was the first seat of government (i.e. capital) of Nigeria during the colonial era. The city of Calabar is significant in Nigerian history in that it has right from time, been known as a place where political and military deportees find refuge. For example, when the colonial masters deported the Oba of Benin, Oba Overanmi, he was sent to Calabar, and recently Charles Taylor was granted asylum in Calabar. Socially, the people of Cross River State are known to be hospitable. Economically, the state has the first Export Processing Zone (EPZ), in the nation and this has indications of a bright economic future. In summary the administration of the State consistently addresses the issue of under-development and tourism.

A simple random sampling technique was used was used to sample 300 respondents (250 females and 50 males). The questionnaire was the primary instrument used to collect data. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results

Socio-demographics

It was recorded that, out of 300 respondents, 13.4% were within the age bracket of 12-16 years, 33.3% represents the age regime of 17-22 years. The age bracket of 23-27 had a representation of 40%. The sample reflects the true empirical situation that commercial sex work attracts people in their "teens" up to the age about 30 years. From the analysis, the class of respondents in the FSLC - JSS3, has a representation of 38.7% and the SSI - OND class represents 43.3%. Those with higher level of education namely/ HND, B.Sc and above account for 18%. It is obvious that the employed population had little or nothing to do with prostitution with a representation of 20%. The unemployed population in the study sample represented 80% showing that, unemployment can cause somebody to prostitute.

Hypothesis testing

There is no significant relationship between poverty and commercial sex work. The statistical measure used was Pearson's Product-moment Correlation coefficient.

Table 1

Variables	Zx	Zx²	Rxy	r-value
P	Xv	Iy²		1
Poverty	985	12988	10984	0.97
Commercial sex	786	9758		

$r^2 = 0.196$ at 0.05 level of significance

From table 1, the calculated value of $r = 0.97$ is greater than the tabulated critical value of 0.196 required at 0.5 level of significance. This means that, the alternate hypothesis that states, there is a significant relationship between poverty and commercial sex work is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that poverty is a key causal factor of prostitution among the female youths in Cross River State. This is statistical shown through the result of the Pearson's product Moment Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.97$). This proven the positive relation between the study variables (poverty and prostitution).

For the sake of triangulation of data, interview was conducted and according to one of the interviewees, who pleaded anonymity, she reported that:

"I am using what I have to get what I want, after all sin is sin... how about those politicians who steal our money, the so-called big men who stand on the road robbed, people... I do this because I cannot do armed robbery and I cannot rig elections and steal."

Discussions

The result as expressed in the hypothesis showed that there is a statistically significant relationship between poverty and susceptibility to prostitution among young girls in Cross River State. From the result of the analysis, it was clear that, overwhelming the respondents unequivocally agreed that, poverty plays a very vital role in commercial sex work. Majority of those involved in this undignified trade, only did, because poverty and hunger have reduced them to mere caricature. The findings however confirmed the view of Odigha (2003), that poverty is worse than HIV/AIDS, and a man who is poor is a risk to the society and can do desperately anything to survive. This is essential because records and research have shown that, poverty and unemployment is a bane of most of the atrocities committed in our society.

This is in line with ministry of national planning recommendation (1080: 20-21) which opines that, to eradicate poverty, development must be cantered on man in the unfolding and the realization of his/her potentials to enable him/her improve his material condition and living through the use the resources available to his disposal.

Conclusion

This study reveals some baseline conclusive information on susceptibility to commercial sex work among teenagers. It should be understood that prostitution is a venture undertaken by both teenagers and averagely disposed youths who remain the most susceptible and vulnerable groups associated with these phenomena. This work confirms the assertion that, prostitution and poverty, lack of access to available resources and opportunities encourage prostitution.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this present study, the following recommendations are made;

- i. Policies and programs meant to affect the life of the citizens should be simple and practicable with grassroots involvement and with a commitment to actually impact on the lives of the prime beneficiaries.
- ii. Government should as a matter of urgency create employment opportunities for her citizenry. This is because 65% of commercial sex workers in the state and Nigeria at large are unemployed persons.
- iii. Parents, religious leaders in various churches and mosques should preach especially to the youths, the benefits of not engaging in prostitution and equally sensitizing them on its ills and dangers.
- iv. Deliberate effort by government should be embarked upon to massively provide employment and create a platform, that both will help generate wealth to the large armies of unemployed Cross Riverians (Nigerians).

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